

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIET THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF OBESITY

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the importance and results of diet therapy in the treatment of morbid obesity, a disease widespread in modern medicine.

At present, most researchers acknowledge that only surgical treatment can achieve stable weight loss and restore patients with obesity to a full life¹. However, it should be noted that there are cases in medicine and clinical practice where diet also yields positive results. In obese individuals, the expansion of the abdomen and the resulting increase in intra-abdominal pressure may predispose them to reflux. However, it is unclear whether randomized controlled trials have been conducted to evaluate the effect of weight loss on reducing reflux symptoms. One study conducted in lean individuals showed that diet-induced weight loss is strongly associated with a reduction in reflux symptoms². Factors Contributing to Obesity:

- Sedentary lifestyle;
- Genetic factors, in particular:
- High activity of lipogenesis enzymes
- Reduced activity of lipolysis enzymes
- Certain diseases, especially endocrine disorders (hypogonadism, hypothyroidism, insulinoma);
- Psychological disorders of eating behavior that lead to abnormal food consumption (e.g., psychogenic overeating);
- Susceptibility to stress;
- Prader-Willi syndrome;
- Hypothalamic dysfunction;
- Lack of sleep;
- Psychotropic medications;

¹ Савельева Л А. Современные подходы к лечению ожирения // Врач.—2001.-№ 1.- С. 12-14; Шурыгин Д.Я., Вязицкий П.О., Сидоров К.А. Ожирение.-Л.-Медицина,1980.-260с.

² Fraser-Moodie CA, Norton B, Gornall C, Magnago S, Weale AR, Holmes GKT. Weight loss has an independent beneficial effect on symptoms of gastro-oesophageal reflux in patients who are overweight. //Scand J Gastroenterol 1999;34:337-340.

- Systemic glucocorticosteroids;
- Hormonal contraceptives;
- Insulin and insulin secretion stimulators.

During evolution, the human body adapted to store nutrients when food was abundant in order to maintain energy during periods of scarcity or forced fasting—this was an evolutionary advantage that allowed humans to survive. In ancient times, obesity was considered a sign of prosperity, sufficiency, fertility, and health.

The long-term results of treatment based on reducing the energy value of the diet are often disappointing (regardless of whether it is carried out under medical supervision or without a doctor's oversight). According to a study conducted by American psychologist Traci Mann and her colleagues, dieting is generally ineffective as a method for combating obesity.

However, it should be emphasized that obesity cannot be successfully treated without proper control of caloric intake. The World Health Organization recommends, for successful weight loss, first calculating the usual calorie intake and then gradually reducing it by 300–500 kcal per month until reaching a level that is 500 kcal below the required amount. For individuals who are not engaged in active physical labor, this value typically ranges from 1500 to 2000 kcal.

Researchers have found that individuals who regularly consume low-fat dairy products tend to gain less excess weight and are less likely to suffer from metabolic syndrome.

The general approach to treating obesity involves trying all known medications used for managing excess weight. Psychotherapeutic treatment (behavioral therapy) is also applied. If pharmacological treatment is insignificant in effect or shows no results at all, it should be discontinued. In such cases, the possibility of surgical intervention may be considered.

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